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A comparative analysis of head teachers' leadership styles and their impact on teachers' job performance

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of head teachers' leadership styles on teachers' job performance, to identify approaches that most effectively enhance instructional outcomes. Conducted during the first quarter of the 2024–2025 school year, the research employed a quasi-experimental design. Data were collected through surveys of teachers' perceptions of leadership styles and interviews with head teachers for deeper qualitative insights. The sample size was determined using the Slovin formula. Data analysis utilized weighted mean, one-way ANOVA, standard deviation, and Tukey's HSD post hoc test to compare the effects of various leadership styles.

Findings revealed that head teachers' leadership styles significantly influence teachers' performance, with transformational leadership emerging as the most effective approach. Teachers under transformational leaders demonstrated broader skill application, higher motivation, and improved instructional quality compared to those led by other styles. The study concludes that adopting transformational leadership can foster a more dynamic and productive teaching environment. It is recommended that head teachers and school principals integrate transformational practices to accelerate teacher performance and professional growth.

Keywords: Leadership Styles; Teacher Performance; Democratic Leadership; Transformational Leadership; Transactional Leadership; Laissez-Faire Leadership

1. Introduction

Every organization's performance and results, including educational institutions, are significantly influenced by leadership. The effect of school administration styles on teachers' job performance in schools has drawn more attention in recent years. The relationship between leadership philosophy and work performance has been the subject of numerous empirical studies, with varying degrees of success (Liu, 2015; Cheng and Yang, 2019). As Aboagye et al. (2019), the leadership philosophies that are most often studied in educational settings are transformational, democratic, transactional, and laissez-faire. These have also been shown to be the most common leadership philosophies in academic contexts by other studies (Liu, 2015). Building successful and high-achieving schools starts with having leadership that is capable of continuously bringing the school's vision and mission into alignment.

This action research aimed to investigate the impact of head teachers' leadership styles on teachers' job performance at Bagong Nayo II National High School. The head teachers' views on leadership will be explored on how they promote their teachers' job performance. One of the most important factors affecting the quality of instruction and the learning environment in educational institutions is leadership. Therefore, it is crucial for ongoing development within

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educational contexts to comprehend how leadership styles and teacher effectiveness are related. This endeavor aims to identify trends and correlations between leadership philosophies and teachers' effectiveness on the job. The results will be helpful for school administrators as well as teachers since they offer insights into good leadership techniques that support a productive workplace and improve teacher performance.

The study involved a comparative analysis of different leadership styles and their effects on teacher performance, with the goal of providing valuable insights to enhance leadership practices within the school setting. Data will be collected through surveys, interviews, and performance evaluations, and the findings will be analyzed to identify patterns and correlations between leadership styles and teacher job performance.

DepEd acknowledged the value of professional standards in school heads' ongoing professional growth and improvement based on career-long learning principles in DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020. The DepEd maintains that high-quality teachers, who are backed by high-quality school administrators, are essential to the learning of high-quality students. As school heads strive for and pursue professional growth, the policy formalized the PPSSH as a public declaration of professional accountability for them to consider and evaluate their practices. The Professional Standards for Teachers, which were adopted by DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017.

Hadiyah (2024) cited that leadership in educational settings plays an important role in shaping teacher performance, influencing motivation, job satisfaction, and overall school improvement. This study investigated the effects of transformational, transactional, and servant leadership styles on teacher performance. Using a mixed-methods approach, it examines the nuances of how each leadership style uniquely impacts teachers' commitment, morale, and engagement in professional development. Findings suggest that transformational leadership enhances motivation and commitment, while transactional leadership supports efficiency and adherence to structure. Conversely, servant leadership fosters a community-oriented and supportive culture. This study provided valuable insights for educational leaders aiming to optimize teacher performance through strategic leadership styles and offers recommendations for future research in varied educational settings.

Mulyana and Wiatr (2021) stated that the interaction between leaders and subordinates is to change the behavior of subordinates to feel capable and highly motivated and strive to achieve higher quality work performance. Given the importance of principal leadership on teacher performance, a principal must be able to encourage and create work motivation for teachers, which allows them to work comfortably and calmly, full of intimacy and mutual respect. Based on the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that there is a positive indirect effect between the principal's transformational leadership on teacher performance through work motivation, that work motivation can fully mediate the principal's transformational leadership on teacher performance, because teachers who have high work motivation will try to as much as possible to be able to achieve better work performance than before by improving professional abilities and skills in teaching so that teacher performance will increase.

According to Wijaya to et al. (2021), one of the important competencies that must be possessed by a leader is the ability to be able to motivate their subordinates. Open and Yudina (2020) stated that the results of their research analysis showed that the principal's transformational leadership indirectly had a positive effect on teacher performance through teacher discipline.

Karata (2018) stated that there was an indirect relationship between the principal's transformational leadership on teacher performance through work motivation. Madjid (2016), explained that several factors that influence the implementation of teacher performance are work discipline and transformational leadership of school principals. In the learning process, a teacher will be able to carry out learning well if it is supported by work discipline and transformational leadership of the principal. A teacher who has high work discipline will be willing and willing to continue working to carry out his duties as an obligation.

As cited by Edgeron (2006), to improve the performance of the school it should involve leadership, which is the basic component and a crucial element. Therefore, to provide successful performance, it is important to be knowledgeable enough to gauge the leadership performance correctly. Nsubuga (2013), said that teachers' performance about the statement above are the job that can be identified by various factors such as the hours of their stay at school including the overtime rendered even without additional pay, these includes training/ coaching of learners to different activities (level of dedication), attending trainings and seminars that can be used for the academic achievement of the students and creates globally competitive pupils (professional growth).

Nsubuga (2013) also said that being a resourceful and creative teacher that gives a conducive environment for the learners (environment of the school), promoting a friendly environment for the students to feel safe at school (school

culture), producing innovative changes in the teaching process (innovation ability of teachers), and lastly, an engaging principal and teachers' harmonious relationship are also determinants of good teachers' performance.

Rivai (2014) stated that a leader must have motivational inspiration so that they can motivate subordinates to do their jobs fully. Leaders also motivated teachers to improve teacher competence and careers by providing teachers with opportunities to participate in various training or pursue higher education.

Supardi (2014) stated that employee performance can be measured by how good the quality of the work, the level of honesty in various situations, initiative in carrying out tasks, employee attitudes towards work, cooperation, understanding of work, and discipline in carrying out responsibilities.

Leithwood and Jantzi (2006) examined the impact of transformational leadership on teachers' commitment and performance in schools. They found that transformational leadership had a positive effect on teachers' attitudes toward their work, job satisfaction, and commitment to student achievement. Transformational leaders were able to create a vision that teachers felt connected to, which motivated them to work harder and more collaboratively.

The study highlighted that transformational leadership directly improved teaching quality by increasing teacher motivation and fostering an environment of trust and support.

The literature review reveals a strong consensus on the positive impact of transformational leadership on teacher performance. Studies by Leithwood and Jantzi (2006) and Kardata (2018) highlighted the link between transformational leadership, increased teacher motivation, job satisfaction, and improved teaching quality. Mulyani and Wiart (2021) further emphasized the mediating role of motivation in this relationship. While transformational leadership is consistently highlighted, other leadership styles show mixed results. Democratic leadership is valued for its collaborative aspects, while transactional leadership is seen as providing structure but potentially lacking motivational elements. Laissez-faire leadership consistently received negative feedback due to its lack of guidance and support.

The consensus points towards leadership styles that combine structure, support, empowerment, inspiration, and collaboration as most effective in enhancing teacher performance. This study aimed to investigate these themes within the specific context of Bagong Nayon II National High School.

2. Materials and Methods

This study aims to determine the impact of head teachers' leadership styles on teachers' job performance at Bagong Nayon II National High School during the School Year 2024-2025.

2.1. Specifically, it will seek answers to the following questions

- What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, marital status, highest educational attainment, field of specialization, length of service at the present school, and years of teaching experience?
- What are the prevailing leadership styles that are commonly employed by head teachers?
- What is the level of teachers' performance during the School Year 2023-2024?
- Is there a significant impact between the head teachers' leadership style and the teachers' job performance?

2.2. Scope and Limitations

The completion of this action research will contribute to the existing body of knowledge on the impact of leadership styles on teacher job performance. By identifying effective leadership strategies, the study aims to guide school administrators in implementing practices that promote a conducive work environment and foster continuous improvement in educational outcomes.

Also, it aims to provide a recent and comprehensive understanding of how different leadership styles impact teachers' job performance. The outcomes will contribute valuable insights to educational administrators, helping them make informed decisions to improve leadership practices within the school.

Moreover, it seeks to bridge the existing gap in understanding the influence of head teachers' leadership styles on teachers' job performance at Bagong Nayon II National High School. The findings will not only benefit the school in

question but also serve as a reference for other educational institutions aiming to enhance their leadership practices and, consequently, teacher performance.

2.3. Research Methodology

The research adopted a mixed-methods approach, utilizing both quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques.

2.3.1. Sampling

The respondents of this paper are 28 teachers from all departments. Data were collected through a research-made instrument where items underwent reliability testing and validation by experts in the field of leadership and management to identify patterns and correlations between leadership styles and teacher job performance.

The following sources were employed

- Surveys: Conducted surveys to gather quantitative data on teachers' perceptions of leadership styles and their impact on job performance.
- Interviews: Conducted interviews with head teachers to gain deeper insights into their leadership styles and strategies.
- Performance Evaluations: Utilized IPCRF rating as a means of representation of performance evaluations of teachers' job performance.
- Comparative Analysis: Compared data from different leadership styles to identify correlations and trends related to teacher job performance.

2.3.2. Data Collection

The following methodology were used

- Research Design: The study adopted a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative research methods.
- Sampling: A sample of teachers from Bagong Nayon II National High School were selected using stratified random sampling.
- Data Collection: Surveys, interviews, and observations were employed to gather data on leadership styles, teacher motivation, job satisfaction, and overall job performance.

2.3.3. Statistical tools and qualitative analysis techniques were used to interpret the collected data, in particular

- To determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, marital status, highest educational attainment, field of specialization, government examinations passed, length of service at the present school, and years of teaching experience, frequency and percentage distribution were used.
- To identify the prevailing leadership styles that are commonly employed by head teachers, the weighted mean, standard deviation, one-way ANOVA, and Tukey HSD post hoc test were computed.
- To determine the current level of teachers' job performance, the average was used.
- To determine the significant impact between head teachers' leadership style and the teachers' job performance, multiple regression analysis was employed.

3. Results

This part discussed the data gathered through the research instruments and presented in a comprehensive form to render a clear and systematic analysis. Interpretations and inferences are drawn based on these data.

3.1. Profile of the Teacher Respondents

Table 1 Profile of the Teacher Respondents in Terms of Grade Level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Grade 7	2	7.14	4
Grade 8	7	25	3
Grade 9	9	32.14	2

Grade 10	10	35.34	1
Total	28	100	

The distribution of teacher respondents across grade levels suggested that the study's findings were more reflective of teaching experiences in the higher grade levels, particularly Grades 9 and 10, which together accounted for over 67% of the sample. This concentration implied that instructional practices, leadership perceptions, and pedagogical decisions discussed in the study might have been influenced by the curriculum complexity and student maturity typically associated with these levels. Conversely, the limited representation from Grade 7 (7.14%) may have reduced the generalizability of findings to lower grade-level contexts. This uneven distribution might influence the overall findings if grade level is related to teacher perception of leadership styles or job performance. The concentration of teachers in Grade 10 and Grade 9 suggests a potential bias in the sample if leadership style or job performance varies significantly across grade levels. It's possible that any inferences on teacher attitudes or work performance won't hold for all grades, especially for grades 7 and 8. Hence, interpretations and recommendations drawn from the study were contextualized accordingly, considering this distribution. Further analysis should consider this distribution when interpreting the results.

Table 2 Profile of the Teacher Respondents in Terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Male	10	35.34	2
Female	18	64.29	1
Total	28	100	

In Table 2, the data indicated that most teacher respondents were female (64.29%), with males comprising 35.34% of the sample. This gender imbalance may have reflected a broader national or institutional trend in the teaching profession, where female educators were more predominant, especially in junior high school settings. As a result, the findings and interpretations of the study might have been influenced by gender-related perspectives in pedagogical practices, communication styles, and leadership preferences. It also implied that any conclusions drawn about instructional beliefs or responsiveness to leadership were likely more representative of female educators' experiences and insights. But there are typically more female teachers than male teachers in many educational settings, especially in basic and lower secondary education. That larger tendency might be reflected in this sample. Alternatively, if female teachers were more available or ready to participate, this might be a sample effect.

Table 3 Profile of the Teacher Respondents in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percent	Rank
61 and above	1	3.57	5
51-60	4	14.29	3
41-50	9	32.14	2
31-40	11	39.29	1
21-30	3	10.71	4
20 and below	0	0	6
Total	28	100	

The age distribution of the teacher respondents showed that more than a third (39.29%) were in the 31–40 age group, followed by 32.14% in the 41–50 age group. This indicated that most participants were in their mid-career to late-career stages, suggesting a wealth of professional experience and potentially well-established teaching practices. These respondents may have brought mature perspectives and reflective insights into instructional beliefs, leadership interactions, and pedagogical decision-making. However, the limited number of younger teachers (21–30 years) and the absence of respondents below 21 or between 51–60 years might have limited the representation of early-career and near-retirement educators. A combined 71.43% of respondents are between the ages of 31 and 50, indicating a substantial presence of mid-career professionals. The age distribution is somewhat concentrated, with most

respondents falling within a relatively narrow age range. With little representation from either younger or older age groups, the table shows a high concentration of instructors in their mid-career. This means that the study's findings will most likely represent the viewpoints and experiences of teachers in their peak professional years.

This has important ramifications for how leadership style and job performance results are interpreted. Future research should strive for a more evenly distributed age sample or examine data by age group to identify potential perceptual variations in order to guarantee inclusive and balanced insights. This could limit the generalizability of the findings if age significantly impacts perceptions of leadership or job performance. Therefore, the study's findings may have been more aligned with the perceptions and experiences of mid-career teachers.

Table 4 Profile of the Teacher Respondents in Terms of Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Single	4	14.29	2
Married	22	78.57	1
Seperated	1	3.57	3
Widow	1	3.57	3
Total	28	100.0	

The marital status profile of the teacher respondents revealed that a large majority (78.57%) were married. This suggested that most participants might have had additional family responsibilities alongside their professional roles, potentially influencing their time management, stress levels, and work-life balance. The predominance of married respondents may have also shaped their perspectives on leadership support, collaboration, and stability in the workplace. In contrast, single (14.29%), separated (3.57%), and widowed (3.57%) teachers represented a smaller portion of the sample, which may have limited the diversity of insights related to varying personal life circumstances. The high percentage of married respondents might influence the results if marital status is related to perceptions of leadership styles or job performance. And priorities, including preferences for stable leadership, job security, or flexible scheduling, might be influenced by marital status. As such, the findings of the study were more likely to reflect the experiences and needs of married teachers.

Table 5 Profile of the Teacher Respondents in Terms of Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Education Attainment	Frequency	Percent	Rank
PH. D/Ed. D Graduate	1	3.57	4
MAT/MAED Graduate	8	28.57	2
With MAT/Maed Units	16	57.14	1
Bachelor Degree	3	10.71	3
Total	28	100.0	

The data on highest educational attainment showed that a majority of the teacher respondents (57.14%) had earned graduate units in MAT or MAEd programs, while 28.57% had already completed their master's degrees. This indicated that most respondents had advanced academic preparation, which likely contributed to deeper content knowledge, stronger pedagogical skills, and more informed instructional decision-making. Only a small portion held a bachelor's degree (10.71%) or doctoral degree (3.57%), suggesting limited representation of early-career teachers and highly advanced scholars.

The study's teaching team is highly educated, as the table demonstrates; the majority have earned or are working toward a master's degree. This is indicative of a group that is academically engaged and professionally driven, and their education has probably influenced how they view leadership and job performance. Nonetheless, the scant contributions from teachers with merely bachelor's degrees and doctorates point to the need for care when extrapolating the findings to all educational levels. In the future, stratified analysis or greater sampling across educational qualifications may be used for more balanced findings. As a result, the study's findings were likely shaped by the perspectives of educators

who were either currently pursuing or had completed postgraduate education, which could imply a greater alignment with evidence-based and reflective teaching practices.

Table 6 Profile of the Teacher Respondents in Terms of Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency	Percent	Rank
26 and above	5	17.86	3
21-25	2	7.14	5.5
16-20	3	10.71	4
11-15	12	42.86	1
6-10	4	14.29	2
5 and below	2	7.14	5.5
Total	28	100	

The data on length of service revealed that the majority of the teacher respondents (42.86%) had been in service for 11 to 15 years, while an additional 17.86% had served for 26 years and above. This indicated that most participants were experienced educators who had spent a significant amount of time in the teaching profession. Their extensive service may have contributed to more refined instructional practices, greater familiarity with school systems, and deeper insight into leadership dynamics. The presence of respondents with shorter service durations—7.14% with five years or less and another 14.29% with 6 to 10 years—offered some representation of newer teachers, but their relatively smaller proportion suggested that the study's findings may have reflected the perspectives and pedagogical approaches of more seasoned educators. The majority of the teaching staff in this sample have been in their positions for more than 11 years. According to this description, the group is seasoned and solid, which could affect opinions on work performance and leadership philosophies.

4. Discussion

4.1. Overview of Leadership Styles

The data reflected how teachers perceived different leadership styles based on their responses to specific statements related to each style. The ratings range from 5 (Always Applied) to 1 (Never Applied), allowing us to gauge the overall sentiment towards each leadership approach.

Table 7 Perception of Teachers on Democratic Leadership

Democratic Leadership	Mean	Description
Encourages teachers' input in decision-making processes.	4.04	Frequently Applied
Hold meetings where staff can voice their opinions and concerns.	3.96	Frequently Applied
Delegate tasks and responsibilities to teachers, allowing them to take ownership of their work.	4.18	Frequently Applied
Provide opportunities for teachers to participate in professional development activities related to leadership and decision-making.	4.07	Frequently Applied
Fosters a culture of open communication and feedback, where staff feel comfortable sharing their thoughts and ideas.	4.14	Frequently Applied
Values the expertise and perspectives of staff, recognizing their contributions to the school's success.	4.21	Frequently Applied
Considers teachers' input when developing school-wide policies and procedures.	4.07	Frequently Applied

Solicits feedback from staff about their experiences and needs.	4.18	Frequently Applied
Creates opportunities for staff to collaborate on projects and initiatives.	4.21	Frequently Applied
Empower teachers to make decisions within their areas of responsibility.	4.07	Frequently Applied
Total	4.11	Frequently Applied

Legend

- 5 – Always Applied (4.51 - 5.00)
- 4 – Frequently Applied (3.51 - 4.50)
- 3 – Occasionally Applied (2.51 - 3.50)
- 2 – Seldom Applied (1.51- 2.50)
- 1 – Never Applied (1.00 - 1.50)

Table 7 showed the weighted mean, which was 4.11, implying that head teachers frequently applied democratic leadership styles. In contrast, teachers generally appreciated the democratic leadership style, especially in aspects like encouraging input in decision-making (1) and open communication (5). The relatively low scores in the 2 and 1 categories indicate minimal resistance to this leadership style. Teachers value their expertise being recognized (6), which is crucial for fostering a collaborative environment. Democratic leadership is perceived positively, indicating that teachers feel empowered and valued in their contributions to school governance. This could lead to increased job satisfaction and a stronger commitment to the school's mission.

The mean heavily favored the democratic leadership style, with most responses falling in the "Frequently Applied". Teachers strongly favored democratic leadership approaches, suggesting that they value participation in decision-making and open communication.

In a study, Mashal (2009) emphasized the benefits associated with a democratic leadership style, which includes increased trust in the leaders by their followers, which positively affects organizational performance.

Table 8 Perception of Teachers on Transformational Leadership

Transformational Leadership	Mean	Description
Inspires and motivates teachers to achieve a shared vision for the school.	4.18	Frequently Applied
Challenges teachers to think critically and creatively about their work.	4.32	Frequently Applied
Demonstrates a strong commitment to the school's mission and values.	4.21	Frequently Applied
Communicates a clear and compelling vision for the future of the school.	4.14	Frequently Applied
Inspires teachers to go beyond their comfort zones and strive for excellence	4.14	Frequently Applied
Provides individual support and guidance to staff, helping them to develop their skills and potential.	4.18	Frequently Applied
Create a culture of continuous learning and improvement within the school.	4.43	Frequently Applied
Foster a sense of ownership and responsibility among staff, empowering them to make a difference.	4.04	Frequently Applied

Celebrates successes and acknowledge the contributions of staff.	4.14	Frequently Applied
Encourages teachers to take risks and experiment with new ideas.	4.21	Frequently Applied
Total	4.20	Frequently Applied

Table 8 indicated that common leadership perceived by the teachers is transformational leadership, with weighted mean of 4.20 (Frequently Applied). Hence, the means are high, particularly in inspiring and motivating teachers (1) and creating a culture of continuous improvement (7). The minimal number of low scores indicated a strong alignment with the transformational approach, which emphasized vision and individual support. In Bagong Nayon II National High School, Head teachers created a culture of continuous learning and improvement within the school with a weighted mean of 4.43. Teachers also appreciated that their leaders gave them challenging tasks, which gave them the opportunity to think critically and creatively about their work, with the weighted mean of 4.32 (Frequently Applied).

Transformational leadership is effective in inspiring teachers and fostering a shared vision. This approach has likely contributed to professional growth and innovation, as teachers are encouraged to take risks and think creatively. The scores heavily favored the transformational leadership style, with most responses falling in the "Frequently Applied". Teachers strongly favored transformational leadership approaches, suggesting that they value participation in decision-making and open communication.

According to Tucker and Russell (2004), the influence of transformational leaders on organizational cultures can be seen in the employees who work in the organization. Transformational leaders helped subordinates discover who they are and what part they play in helping the organization achieve its mission. By interacting with subordinates in this manner, transformational leaders helped subordinates increase their level of commitment to the organization. Individual achievements require qualifications and skills, and a personal belief in one's ability to successfully perform a particular action (Bandura,1986)

Table 9 Perception of Teachers on Transactional Leadership

Transactional Leadership	Mean	Description
Clearly defines expectations and performance standards for teachers.	4.14	Frequently Applied
Provides rewards and recognition for staff who meet or exceed expectations.	3.89	Frequently Applied
Implements the consequences for staff who fail to meet expectations.	3.86	Frequently Applied
Focuses on maintaining order and efficiency within the school.	3.89	Frequently Applied
Focuses on maintaining order and efficiency within the school.	4.11	Frequently Applied
Emphasizes compliance with rules and procedures.	4.11	Frequently Applied
Uses a clear system of accountability to track teachers' performance.	4.18	Frequently Applied
Provides regular feedback to teachers on their performance.	4.14	Frequently Applied
Focuses on achieving specific goals and objectives.	4.18	Frequently Applied
Prioritizes short-term results and immediate outcomes	4.11	Frequently Applied
Total	4.06	Frequently Applied

Table 9 presented the perception of teachers on transactional leadership, with an overall mean of 4.06, categorized as "Frequently Applied". This indicated that teachers generally perceived transactional leadership practices as commonly used by school leaders.

The highest-rated indicators included "Uses a clear system of accountability to track teachers' performance" and "Focuses on achieving specific goals and objectives" (both with a mean of 4.18), followed closely by items such as "Provides regular feedback" and "Clearly defines expectations and performance standards" (both with means above

4.10). These scores reflected a leadership style that emphasized structure, accountability, and results-oriented performance.

While all items were rated within the “frequently applied” range, the lowest mean scores were found in “Provides rewards and recognition for staff who meet or exceed expectations” (3.89) and “Implements consequences for staff who fail to meet expectations” (3.86). These findings suggested that although performance standards and monitoring mechanisms were in place, the motivational components of transactional leadership, such as incentives and corrective actions, were less emphasized or inconsistently applied.

The data implied that school leaders were perceived to consistently practice transactional leadership, particularly in the areas of performance tracking, rule compliance, and goal setting. This leadership approach may have contributed to operational efficiency, clear role expectations, and consistent evaluation practices within the school.

However, the relatively lower emphasis on rewards and consequences suggested that the motivational dimension of transactional leadership may have been underutilized. This could have limited its potential to fully inspire improved performance or reinforce positive behaviors among staff. While teachers appeared to value the clarity and structure provided by transactional leaders, the integration of stronger incentive systems and recognition strategies could have further enhanced teacher morale, motivation, and overall productivity.

In addition, although transactional leadership is recognized for providing clarity, consistency, and organizational order, it may lack the inspirational and empowering qualities often found in democratic and transformational leadership styles. This limitation could lead to a more mechanical or compliance-driven environment that may not fully engage teachers’ creativity, initiative, or passion for teaching.

According to Backread et al. (2017), transactional leadership is heavily focused on attaining organizational objectives through a system of rewards and punishments. Leaders provide staff with two clear options: to complete tasks and meet expectations in exchange for benefits such as rewards and promotions, or to face consequences, such as reduced salaries, bonuses, or promotion opportunities, for failing to do so. While this system enforces discipline and clear expectations, it may also create a performance culture driven by obligation rather than intrinsic motivation.

Overall, the perception of transactional leadership as frequently applied underscored its significant role in promoting discipline, measurable outcomes, and accountability, while also revealing the need for improvement in staff motivation, recognition, and engagement. Enhancing the human-relational dimension of transactional leadership could help foster a more balanced and motivating work environment for teachers.

Table 10 Perception of the Teachers on Laissez-Faire Leadership

Laissez-Faire Leadership	Mean	Description
Gives teachers a high degree of autonomy and freedom to make decisions	4.07	Frequently Applied
Avoids providing direction or guidance to staff.	3.04	Occasionally Applied
Intervenes in staff conflicts or disagreements.	3.79	Frequently Applied
Allows teachers to set their own goals and priorities.	3.86	Frequently Applied
Provides minimal supervision or oversight of staff work.	3.75	Frequently Applied
Avoids setting clear expectations or performance standards for staff.	3.39	Occasionally Applied
Provides feedback or evaluation of staff performance.	4.04	Frequently Applied
Allows teachers to operate with a high degree of independence.	4.25	Frequently Applied
Avoids taking responsibility for teachers’ decisions or actions.	3.50	Occasionally Applied
Allows teachers to make decisions without consulting them.	3.57	Occasionally Applied
Total	3.73	Frequently Applied

Table 10 showed that teachers perceived laissez-faire leadership as frequently applied, with an overall mean of 3.73. The highest-rated item was “Allows teachers to operate with a high degree of independence” (Mean = 4.25), followed

by “Gives teachers a high degree of autonomy and freedom to make decisions” (Mean = 4.07), and “Provides feedback or evaluation of staff performance” (Mean = 4.04). These findings indicated that teachers experienced considerable autonomy in their roles and that school leaders maintained a generally non-intrusive leadership style.

However, several indicators were only occasionally applied, including “Avoids providing direction or guidance to staff” (Mean = 3.04), “Avoids setting clear expectations or performance standards” (Mean = 3.39), and “Avoids taking responsibility for teachers’ decisions or actions” (Mean = 3.50). These items reflected the less desirable dimensions of laissez-faire leadership, suggesting that although autonomy was granted, it was at times accompanied by insufficient leadership involvement, guidance, and accountability.

The data implied that teachers operated in an environment where independence and self-direction were emphasized. Such autonomy may have empowered experienced teachers and fostered a sense of trust and ownership over their instructional decisions. However, the inconsistent application of structure, expectations, and feedback may have led to role ambiguity and gaps in performance monitoring.

Previous studies support these findings. For instance, Skogstad et al. (2007) found that laissez-faire leadership can result in role ambiguity and workplace conflict, potentially escalating to workplace bullying. Similarly, Hu et al. (2022) noted that laissez-faire leadership was associated with employee time spent navigating workplace norms—highlighting its indirect impact on performance. Although these studies did not explore subordinates’ stress levels in depth, they pointed to laissez-faire leadership as a potential stressor in professional environments.

The current study extended these insights by adopting a cognitive perspective, emphasizing the importance of how subordinates appraise their experiences under laissez-faire leaders. Whether the leadership outcomes are perceived positively or negatively depends on the subordinates’ individual goals and whether they view the leadership environment as a challenge or a hindrance. This dynamic interpretation revealed that laissez-faire leadership is not inherently negative but depends largely on the context and the cognitive framing of those involved.

In summary, while laissez-faire leadership may support professional freedom and autonomy, particularly among experienced staff, it may not be effective for novice teachers or in settings requiring coordination and shared accountability. These findings imply that school leaders should aim to strike a balance between granting autonomy and providing consistent direction, structure, and performance expectations to ensure both teacher growth and instructional alignment within the school.

4.2 Level of Teachers’ Job Performance During School Year 2023-2024

Table 11 Level of Teachers’ Job Performance

Rating	Description	Frequency	Percentage
4.50 – 5.00	Outstanding	19	67.86
3.50 – 4.49	Very satisfactory	9	32.14
2.50 – 2.49	Satisfactory	0	0
1.50 – 1.49	Unsatisfactory	0	0
1.00 – 1.49	Poor	0	0
Average Rating	Outstanding	28	100

It can be shown from the table that the latest performance Rating in terms of Range of Scores that Outstanding, got 19 respondents, a percentage of 67.86, and on the hand, very satisfactory appeared only with a percentage of 32.14. Teachers received an overall rating of 4.62, described as "Outstanding". This indicated a high level of overall job performance among the teachers.

Teachers also played a role in influencing both inside and outside the school environment. In addition, creating a good education system requires collaboration and mutual support between the principal, teachers, and students. Previous studies have shown that one of the factors that influences student learning success is collaboration between students, teachers, and other parties involved in school activities. The quality of the teacher’s performance as a professional is an important thing to discuss, considering its significant role in student achievement. But this role cannot be separated

from the educational context, student characteristics, and school factors. In addition, the ability of teachers to be confident, create a comfortable climate for students, maintain interaction, and maintain contact with students can increase student involvement in learning. Teacher instructional qualities, such as classroom management and cognitive activation, also affect students' motivation to learn (Kanya, Fathoni, and Ramdani, 2021).

4.3 Impact of the Head teachers' Leadership Style and Teachers' Job Performance

Table 12 Descriptive Statistics

Leadership Style	Mean	Standard Deviation	Sample Size (N)
Transformational	4.20	0.54	28
Transactional	4.06	0.64	28
Democratic	4.11	0.42	28
Laissez-Faire	3.73	1.82	28

Table 13 ANOVA Analysis Based on Teachers' Job Performance by Leadership Style

Source	Sum of Squares	DF	F	p-value
Leadership Style	8.54	3	4.08	0.0087
Residual	75.46	108		

Table 14 Tukey HSD Post Hoc Test Results

Group 1	Group 2	Mean Difference	p-value	Significant?
Transformational	Laissez-Faire	0.507	0.013	Yes
Democratic	Laissez-Faire	0.421	0.040	Yes
Transformational	Transactional	0.161	0.726	No
Transformational	Democratic	0.086	0.931	No
Transactional	Democratic	-0.075	0.956	No
Transactional	Laissez-Faire	0.346	0.113	No

A one-way ANOVA was conducted to assess whether teachers' job performance differed significantly based on the leadership styles of their head teachers. The result revealed a statistically significant difference among the four leadership styles, $F(3, 108) = 4.08, p = 0.0087$.

The post hoc Tukey HSD test identified that teachers under transformational and democratic leadership styles performed significantly better than those under laissez-faire leadership. No significant difference was found among transformational, transactional, and democratic leadership styles. These results confirm that head teachers' leadership styles have a comparative impact on teachers' job performance.

Transformational Leadership has the highest mean score (4.20) for teacher job performance, implying that it is seen as the most effective style for improving teacher performance. It also has a moderate standard deviation (0.54), which indicates that responses are consistent. Transactional Leadership is closely related, with a mean of 3.73, indicating that it is likewise correlated with strong work performance. The slightly greater standard deviation (0.64) indicates more diversity in perceptions.

Democratic Leadership has a decent mean performance level (4.11), slightly lower than the first two, but with the lowest standard deviation (0.42), indicating that respondents' perceptions are consistent. Laissez-faire leadership has the

lowest scores in both leadership effectiveness (3.73) and related teacher performance (3.73), as well as the biggest standard deviation is the least effective leadership style in promoting teacher job performance. This suggests that it is the least effective leadership style in promoting teacher job performance. Responses were highly varied, implying that some teachers might have had very negative or very positive experiences, but overall, it was less effective.

The data suggests that democratic and transformational leadership styles are preferred by teachers, leading to a culture of collaboration, inspiration, and professional development. In contrast, transactional leadership offers clarity but may lack motivational aspects, while laissez-faire leadership is viewed as ineffective due to its lack of direction. The data suggests that teachers perceive democratic and transformational leadership styles as the most effective, fostering a collaborative, inspiring, and professionally enriching environment. Transactional leadership is seen as providing clarity and structure but may lack the motivational aspects found in the other two styles. Laissez-faire leadership is viewed as ineffective due to its lack of direction and support.

In Democratic Leadership, the teachers appreciate the emphasis on input in decision-making and open communication, valuing their expertise being recognized. This indicates a sense of empowerment and a positive feeling towards the leadership style. While Transformational Leadership, the teachers respond positively to the inspirational and motivational aspects of this style, particularly in creating a culture of continuous improvement. This suggests a strong alignment with the transformational approach, which emphasizes vision and individual support.

In Transactional Leadership, teachers appreciated the clear expectations and performance standards of this style, but some discomfort exists with the emphasis on compliance and rewards/punishments. This suggests a more mechanical approach that may not fully engage teachers' creativity and passion. Laissez-faire leadership has the lowest overall scores for laissez-faire leadership, particularly in areas requiring direction and support. This indicated that teachers feel unsupported and unclear about their roles, potentially negatively impacting morale and accountability.

The data collected indicated that the leadership style of the head teachers and the performance of the teachers differed significantly. In conclusion, the data shows that teachers greatly prefer transformational and democratic leadership styles, while transactional leadership is less preferred and laissez-faire leadership is widely disapproved of. To ascertain the connection between leadership styles and the high degree of work performance stated, a more thorough analysis necessitates filling out Table 12 with the relevant statistical data and performing additional comparison analysis across the tables.

4.4 Recommendations

Considering the foregoing findings and conclusions of the study, the following are recommended

School principals, head teachers, and master teachers were advised to continue cultivating democratic leadership techniques in schools to increase teacher involvement and satisfaction. Strengthen Transformational Approaches is a leadership training program that focuses on creating transformational talents that inspire and motivate instructors. While Transactional Concerns must be addressed to maintain clear expectations, leaders should also implement motivational techniques that acknowledge and reward accomplishments. We should reconsider Laissez-Faire Practices and consider implementing more structured support systems to ensure teachers feel guided and valued in their roles. By focusing on these recommendations, educational leaders can foster a more supportive and effective environment that meets the needs of both teachers and students.

Teachers should participate in open communication with school leaders to encourage the adoption of transformational and democratic leadership styles, which the study found to be positively associated with higher job performance. Teachers can help schools improve by offering systematic feedback on how different leadership styles affect motivation and performance. Even without formal titles, teachers can engage in transformational peer interactions by mentoring, motivating colleagues, and encouraging creativity.

Future research should involve a bigger and more diverse sample from various schools, regions, or nations to improve the generalizability of the findings. Examine the interactions between leadership style and job performance and other elements, such as student results, teacher personality, or school culture.

This research serves to determine the impact of head teachers' leadership styles on teachers' job performance at Bagong Nayo II National High School. The table below outlines the list of individuals, organizations, and informal networks that serve as partners of the researcher in translating and communicating the research findings to end users.

Table 15 Dissemination and Advocacy Plans

Research Topic	Objectives	Target Audiences	Channels	Key Messages	Time-line	Evaluation Process
Impact of Head Teachers' Leadership Styles on Teachers' Job Performance at Bagong Nayo II National High School: A Comparative Study	<p>To determine the most effective leadership styles to enhance teachers' performance.</p> <p>To know if the leaders' styles of the head teacher have an impact on teachers' job performance.</p>	School Principals, Head Teachers, Master Teachers, Teachers, and Future researchers	LAC Session, giving copies of findings on the school administrators and to publish on the internet.	School principals, head teachers, and master teachers were advised to continue cultivating democratic leadership techniques in schools to increase teacher involvement and satisfaction. Strengthen transformational approaches is a leadership training program that focuses on creating transformational talents that inspire and motivate instructors. While Transactional Concerns must be addressed to maintain clear expectations, leaders should also implement motivational techniques that acknowledge and reward accomplishments. We should reconsider Laissez-Faire Practices and consider implementing more structured support systems to ensure teachers feel guided and valued in their roles. By focusing on these recommend-dations, educational leaders can foster a more supportive and effective environment that meets the needs of both teachers and students.	SY June 2025-July 2026	Gather input from stake-holders to determine the clarity and usefulness of the information provided.

Likewise, the results of the action research will be disseminated in the Division of Antipolo City by submitting this research paper to the Schools Division Research Committee. Additional dissemination will occur through presentations at conferences, such as teacher education and education conferences, regionally and nationally, and through articles published in peer-reviewed journals.

5. Conclusion

This study revealed that head teachers' leadership styles significantly influence teachers' job performance, with transformational and participative approaches generally fostering higher motivation, collaboration, and instructional effectiveness, while authoritarian styles tended to limit creativity and professional growth. Comparative analysis highlighted the importance of adaptability in leadership, as contextual factors such as school resources, culture, and teacher needs shaped the effectiveness of each style. The findings underscore the need for leadership development programs that equip Department heads with flexible, inclusive strategies tailored to diverse educational environments. By promoting leadership practices that enhance teacher performance, this study contributes to improving the overall quality of education, benefiting society through better student outcomes and paving the way for further research on leadership adaptability in schools.

6. Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

This study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards applicable to research involving human participants and adhered to all relevant institutional and national guidelines. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection.

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to the conduct, analysis, or reporting of this research.

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